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Florentín Smarandache

Florentin Smarandache is Professor Asociado de Matemática to the [University](#) of New Mexico in EE. Publicó more than 75 books and 100 articuculos and notes of mathematician, physicist, philosophy, psychology, Literature, rebus. In mathematical his [investigation](#) it is in theory of numbers, not-Euclidean geometry, synthetic geometry, algebraic structures, statistic, neutrosofica logic and joint (generalization of blurred intuicionistica logic and joint respectively), neutrosofica probability (generalization of vague and classic probability). Also, few contributions to nuclear and physical of particles, [information](#) of fusion (it sees the theory of Dezert-Smarandache of reasonable reasoning paradojisto and, 2002), philosophy (it sees neutrosofía, a generalización of dialectic), psychology (leya of sensations and stimuli), sociology (paradoxical sociologicales), linguistic (paradoxical semantic and tautología) etc. In [Literature](#) the movement established in 1980 Paradoxismo, based of the use excess of

contradictions, antinomies, paradoxes in creation.

In the art, like one it ironically protests against arbitrary art where [everything](#) was considered like art, defendó for Art-external that means a work of the art the other way around, that is to make art like ugly, like stupid, as incorrect as possible, and generally as impossible as possible.

In philosophy generalized in 1995 dialectic to [Neutrosofía](#), what is a new branch of philosophy that studies the origin, nature, and reach of neutralities, also its interaction with different ideacional phantom. This theory considers each notion or devises along with its opposite or negation and the phantom of "neutralities" (that is slight [knowledge](#) or located ideas enter both extreme, supporting neither nor). The [together](#) ideas and are sent like . According to this theory each idea tends to be neutralized and to be [balanced](#) by ideas and -como an equilibrium state.

Design an algorithm of the [Unification](#) of Theories of Fusion and rules (UFT) used in the medicine, robotics, military man.

On the [physicist](#) it founded a series of paradoxes (it sees the paradoxes of Smarandache quantum), and emitted the hypothesis very controversy between scientists. Also, it considered the possibility of a third form of matter, is called unmateria, that is a [combination](#) of matter and antimatter (or quarks and antiquarks).

In the [mathematical](#) one it created many sequences and functions in the theory of numbers. It presented/displayed [the degree](#) of negation of an axiom or a theorem of geometry (it sees the geometry of Smarandache that can parcialmente be partially Euclidean and not-Euclidean, 1969), the multi-structure (sees it n-structures of Smarandache, where a weak structure contains an island of a strong structure), and multi-space (a combination of spaces heterogenous).

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